

Student Perceptions and Attitudes Toward AI Integration in Higher Education

Dear Respondent,

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this survey.

Ashesi University, a member of a global consortium comprising the World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE), the Institute for International Education (IIE) and seven universities around the world, is conducting a research study on the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on higher education and the workforce in Africa. The study aims to understand how AI is currently influencing teaching and learning, institutional support and strategies for the integration of AI in higher education, as well as the evolving needs of employers as AI becomes more integrated into the world of work.

As a student, you are invited to answer the following questions to provide insights into your perceptions and experiences with AI technologies, institutional interventions and policies, and prospects for future use of AI. The estimated time for completing the survey is 5 to 9 minutes.

Participation in this research study is voluntary. By filling and submitting this form, you are consenting to the collection and use of the data provided for research purposes. Be assured that your responses are completely anonymous and will be aggregated with other responses for reporting purposes. You may choose to stop participating at any time, without any penalty, before you click the "submit" button of the survey. There are no foreseen risks in participating in this survey.

This study and consent form has been reviewed and approved by the Ashesi IRB for Human Subjects Research (Application Number 52024). For further information, please contact the committee at irb@ashesi.edu.gh. You may also contact the Principal Investigators for this study through akorsah@ashesi.edu.gh.

Thank you for your time and contribution to this important research.

* Required

Section 1 of 6: Demographic Information

1. What is your age? *

- Under 20
- 20-24
- 25-29
- 30 and above

2. Sex? *

- Male
- Female

3. Type of academic institution *

- Public University
- Private University
- Public Technical University

4. Name of academic institution *

- Accra Technical University
- Ashesi University
- University of Ghana
- Other

5. What is your academic level? *

- Undergraduate First Year
- Undergraduate Second Year
- Undergraduate Third Year
- Undergraduate Fourth Year
- Master's Student
- PhD Student
- Other

6. What is your primary academic discipline? *

- Computer Science/Computer Engineering
- Other Information Technology related disciplines
- Other Engineering disciplines
- Business/Social Sciences
- Arts/Humanities
- Natural/Applied Sciences
- Medical/Health-related disciplines
- Other

Section 2 of 6: Awareness and Usage of AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to technology that allows machines to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence, such as learning, decision-making, and problem-solving. AI tools include **generative tools** (e.g. **ChatGPT, Gemini, Midjourney**), **voice assistants** (e.g., **Siri, Alexa**), **recommendation systems** (e.g., **Netflix, YouTube**), **navigation apps** (e.g., **Google Maps**), etc.

7. How familiar are you with Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies/ tools? *

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar

8. How did you become familiar with these AI technologies/tools? Select all that apply *

- Training
- News
- Friends
- Social Media
- School
- Other

9. How frequently do you use AI? *

- Never - I do not use AI tools at all
- Rarely - I use AI tools infrequently
- Sometimes - I use AI tools from time to time
- Often - I regularly use AI tools
- Almost Always - I use AI tools quite frequently

10. Which AI tools have you used? (Select all that apply) *

- Chatbots (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini)
- AI-based research tools (e.g., SciSpace, Elicit, Phind)
- Data analysis tools (e.g., Tableau, Power BI)
- AI writing assistants (e.g., Grammarly, Quilbot)
- Image / Video Generation (DALL-E)
- Presentation Preparation (Gamma, Canva etc)
- Homework Assistance Tools
- Personalized Learning Tools
- Other

Section 3 of 6: Awareness and Usage of AI

AI proficiency means knowing how to use and understand AI tools and technologies. It includes being able to work with AI systems or software to solve problems or complete tasks effectively.

11. How proficient are you with the AI tools you selected? *

- Not at all proficient
- Slightly proficient
- Somewhat proficient
- Moderately proficient
- Very proficient

12. How would you describe your level of expertise with AI technologies and tools? *

- Basic Understanding** - I have a fundamental knowledge of AI concepts but have not used AI tools extensively.
- User** - I have utilized AI tools for simple tasks or applications in my work or studies.
- Adaptor** - I can adapt AI tools to solve specific problems and have experience using APIs and other resources.
- Developer** - I actively develop or create AI technologies, such as training models and implementing AI solutions.
- Innovator** - I am a producer of AI technologies, leading projects or creating new AI applications and systems.

13. How frequently do you use AI tools in your **graded** academic work (e.g., assignments, projects, research)? *

- Never - I do not use AI tools at all
- Rarely - I use AI tools infrequently
- Sometimes - I use AI tools from time to time in my work
- Often - I regularly use AI tools for my graded academic work
- Almost Always - I use AI tools quite frequently for my graded academic work

14. How frequently do you use AI tools in your **non-graded** academic work (e.g. self-study, practice, research)? *

- Never - I do not use AI tools at all
- Rarely - I use AI tools infrequently
- Sometimes - I use AI tools from time to time in my work
- Often - I regularly use AI tools for my non-graded academic work
- Almost Always - I use AI tools quite frequently for my non-graded academic work

15. If you have used AI for academic work (either graded or non-graded), what have you used it for? (Select all that apply) *

- Research assistance (e.g., finding sources, summarizing articles)
- Writing support (e.g., drafting essays, grammar checks)
- Data analysis (e.g., processing or analyzing datasets)
- Problem-solving (e.g., coding help, solving equations)
- Study aid (e.g., flashcards, personalized learning recommendations)
- Presentation creation (e.g., generating slides, designing visuals)
- Project planning or organization (e.g., task management, brainstorming)
- Tutoring or learning new topics (e.g., explanations, answering questions)
- Other

16. In your usage of AI, to what extent has it met your expectations? *

- Far below expectations
- Below expectations
- Meets expectations
- Above expectations
- Far exceeds expectations

Section 4 of 6: Perceptions of AI in Learning

17. Do you think AI tools have or can enhance your learning experience? *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

18. In your opinion, what are the benefits of using AI in your studies? (Select all that apply) *

- Improved research efficiency (e.g., faster access to information)
- Enhanced writing quality (e.g., grammar checks, style suggestions)
- Personalized learning experiences (e.g., tailored study materials)
- Saves time on routine tasks (e.g., drafting emails)
- Greater accessibility (e.g., tools for students with disabilities)
- Keeping up with technological advancements
- None
- Other

19. What are your concerns about using AI in education? (Select all that apply): *

- It may replace critical thinking skills
- Ethical concerns about AI-generated content
- Privacy and data security concerns
- Inaccuracy or unreliability of AI tools
- Potential for bias in AI algorithms
- Dependence on AI for academic work
- Misuse of AI for cheating or plagiarism
- Lack of transparency in AI decision-making
- Decreased engagement with traditional learning methods
- Job displacement
- None
- Other

Section 5 of 6: AI in Your Future Career

20. How likely are you to use AI tools in your professional career? *

- Very Unlikely
- Unlikely
- Neutral
- Likely
- Very Likely

21. Learning to use AI tools can improve your career readiness *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

22. Do you think AI may replace humans in the discipline you're currently studying? *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

23. Share your thoughts on the answer you chose for the previous question

Section 6 of 6: Institutional Interventions and Policies

24. How important do you believe it is for your institution to integrate AI tools and systems into its curriculum? *

- Very unimportant
- Unimportant
- Neutral
- Important
- Very important

25. Has your institution subscribed to/acquired AI tools and infrastructure to support or augment teaching and learning? *

- No
- Yes
- Unsure

26. If yes, give some examples

27. Your institution has clear policies regarding the use of AI in teaching or academic work. *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

28. Your institution has clear policies regarding the use of AI in research work. *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

29. Comment on the adequacy or suitability of your institution's policy regarding the use of AI.